

Assessment Of Knowledge Attitudes And Practice About Vitamin D Among Medical And Dental Students In Peshawar

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Abstract

Background: Vitamin D deficiency is a global epidemic. Pakistan is among the highest reported countries having high rate vitamin D deficiency. There are limited exploration of vitamin D related knowledge, attitudes and practices among dental and medical students in Pakistan.

Methods: A descriptive, cross-sectional was conducted among medical and dental students of two private medical institutions in Peshawar, Pakistan. Based on the Raosoft online calculator, it was anticipated that the sample of 169 students would enable us to achieve the study objective. Participants were asked questions about vitamin D using an online pre-validated questionnaire.

Results: A total of 169 students responded. The students were grouped in three age group, age 16-20, age 21-24 and age 25 and above. Out of these 169 student 122 (72.2%) were female students and rest 47 (27.8%) were male. 81 (47.9%) were BDS students and 88 (52%) were MBBS students. When asked whether indoor workers are at a high risk of vitamin D deficiency or not, 91.7% answer correctly. Similarly, 75.7% knew that vitamin D taken more than the recommended amount may be harmful. Elderly people are more prone. 85.2% people realized that vitamin D deficiency occur more in elderly people. 82.2% of students identified that pregnant and lactating women's need of vitamin D is increased due to their condition. 92.2% know that bone ache and fatigue is a sign of vitamin D deficiency. Majority of the students reported that sun exposure is prevented by urbanization (77.4%). Vitamin D mainly is produced by sunlight falling on the skin. Skin has cholesterol that is converted to 7-dehydrocholesterol a precursor of vitamin D. A shortage in public places and full-time indoor occupation prevents the optimal exposure to the sun, making it difficult for the body to make vitamin D. This fact was realized by a bulk of the students participating in the study. 86.4% reported that shortage of public places prevents the sun exposure required for the production of vitamin D. Similarly 91.2% acknowledged the fact that full-time indoor occupation is harmful as well. The attitude of medical and dental students towards vitamin D was not to the point as only 10(5.8%) were taking vitamin D supplements and 14(8.3%) were consuming milk and foods rich in vitamin D. 26(15.5%) use sunscreens on their face 17(10%) on their hands regularly. Similarly their exposure to the sun and their outdoor activities are very limited.

Conclusion: The medical and dental students of Peshawar were generally having good knowledge about vitamin D and the implications of vitamin D deficiency on our daily life. However, their attitudes and practices regarding vitamin D could be considered moderate. Despite the fact that they were medical and dental students, these statistics were not up to the mark. Such outcomes pose two dangers, both of which must be addressed at all costs. Firstly, it would almost certainly cause vitamin D deficiency in those students, particularly ladies. Second, medical students are the guardians of their country's health; therefore their indifference to such a vital vitamin is inexcusable. Future studies should focus on strategies to make the knowledge about vitamin D more applicable in day to day life.

Introduction

Vitamin D deficiency is a global epidemic(1,2). Southeast Asians are being the most affected population(1). According to the National nutritional survey 2018, 13.2% of children under age of five are severely vitamin

deficient and 22.4% are vitamin D deficient in Pakistan. 54% of general population of Pakistan and 25.7% population is affected by vitamin D deficiency(3). Sunlight exposure is the main source of vitamin D, other dietary sources are oily fish, egg yolks and vitamin D dietary supplements(1). The best thing about vitamin D is that it can be synthesized, when skin is exposed to the UVB radiation from the sun(2). Although, all through the year there is plenty sunlight throughout the day in their nations, but still South Asians stay one of the most weak populations to experience the deleterious effects of low levels of vitamin D(4,5).

Vitamin D is important for mineral metabolism(6,7) Studies revealed that low levels of vitamin D are related to various types of cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, chronic kidney diseases and muscle metabolism(7–10). Its insufficiency, causes rickets and is also associated with lower respiratory tract infection in infancy and childhood(11–14). Vitamin D is essential for bone health(15). Irritable bowel syndrome is also a consequence of vitamin D deficiency(16). It has been reported that vitamin D plays a vital role in moderated to severe traumatic brain injury(6).

Several studies reported that South Asians population is highly vitamin D deficient(17–19). Similarly, several studies indicated the deficiency of vitamin D in Pakistani population that included asymptomatic adult population, newborns and females in their reproductive age(5). Different biological factors for serum vitamin D deficiency are known but not much have been done in terms of investigating the Knowledge, Attitude or Practices towards vitamin D in South Asian population.

Methodology

A descriptive, cross-sectional was conducted among medical and dental students of two medical institutions in September 2020-January 2021, in Peshawar, Pakistan. All students who were registered at Rehman medical College, Rehman Dental College, Peshawar Medical College and Peshawar dental College, were invited to participate in this research.

Based on the Raosoft online calculator, it was anticipated that the sample of 169 students would enable us to achieve the study objective. Raosoft online calculator is designed specifically for population surveys to calculate the sample size and determine how many responses are needed, to meet the desired confidence level with the margin of error (usually 5%). In order to achieve a confidence level of 95% and a 5% margin of error, a minimum sample size 169 was required. We emailed the questionnaire to 300 students. They were explained the importance of this study and were encouraged to participate. A constant form was also emailed where they only had to write their first name if they wished to participate. Only 170 responded back with a filled questionnaire. As 169 was the required to achieve the objective, hence, one was dropped out.

Participants were asked questions about vitamin D using an online pre-validated questionnaire. The questions were divided in to three categories: Knowledge, attitude and practices towards vitamin D. the participants were asked to read and accept the consent online upon opening the online survey platform.

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20. Various responses were separated in to different sub groups. The mean and standard deviations (SD) for the continuous data like age. To represent the categorical data like demographic location, percentages were used. Where required, $P \leq 0.5$ was considered significant. The main outcomes of this study were knowledge of food sources, factors effecting vitamin D production, health beneficent of vitamin D and the supplements implications and uses.

Results

A total of 169 students responded. The students were grouped in three age group, age 16-20, age 21-24 and age 25 and above. Out of these 169 student 122 (72.2%) were female students and rest 47 (27.8%) were male. 81 (47.9%) were BDS students and 88 (52%) were MBBS students. The mean age was 21 (SD±4). General characteristics of the students is summarized in Table 1.

Table.1 Characteristics of participants

Parameter	N%
Age in categories (YEARS)	
16-20	104 (62.5%)
21-24	63 (37%)
25 and above	2 (0.5%)
Gender	
Male	122 (72.2%)
Female	47 (27.8)
Course	
MBBS	88 (52.1%)
BDS	81 (47.9%)

Vitamin D deficiency is considered a worldwide effecting different age groups located at different locations. To improve the situation the first step is to understand the level of understanding of students about this pandemic. For this all the 169 students were asked whether vitamin D deficiency is of the most important health issues of the day or not.

Figure.1 showing the answers in response to the question: currently, vitamin D deficiency is one of the most important health issues in our country

To know about the level of knowledge attitude and practices of these dental and medical students' different questions were asked. A detailed list of the questions and responses to those questions are given in Table.2. When asked whether indoor workers are at a high risk of vitamin D deficiency or not, 91.7% answer correctly. Similarly, 75.7% knew that vitamin D taken more than the recommended amount may be harmful. As elderly people are more prone. 85.2% people realized that vitamin D deficiency occur more in elderly people. 82.2% of students identified that pregnant and lactating women's need of vitamin D is increased due to their condition. 92.2% know that bone ache and fatigue is a sign of vitamin D deficiency.

Table.2 Questionnaire used to determine knowledge, attitudes and practices of study participants regarding dietary supplements.

Serial number	Questions	Students	P value
1.	Do people, who work indoors, are at high risk of vitamin D deficiency		
Yes		155 (91.7%)	0.05*
No		9 (5.3%)	
Don't know		5 (3%)	
2.	Is vitamin D intake more than dietary recommendations could be harmful?		
Yes		128(75.7%)	0.04*
No		19(11.2%)	
Don't know		22(13%)	
3.	Are elderly people are at high risk of vitamin D deficiency?		
Yes		144(85.2%)	0.002*
No		8(4.7%)	
Don't know		17(10.1%)	
4.	Is inappropriate dietary intakes are related to vitamin D deficiency?		
Yes		105(62.1%)	0.0194*
No		32(18.9%)	
Don't know		32(18.9%)	
5.	Does vitamin D supplement intake requirements, differ for different age groups?		
Yes		142(84%)	0.039*
No		12(7.1%)	
Don't know		15(8.9%)	
6.	Are pregnant and lactating women are at high risk of vitamin D deficiency?		
Yes		140(82.8%)	0.05*
No		9(5.3%)	
Don't know		20(11.8%)	
7.	Most of the vitamin D required is produced when the skin is directly exposed to the sun		
Yes		156(92.3%)	0.009*
No		7(4.1%)	
Don't know		6(3.6%)	
8.	Bone pain and fatigue are among the vitamin D deficiency symptoms		
Yes		157(92.9)	0.028*

No		6(3.6%)	
Don't know		6(3.6%)	
9.	Vitamin D supplement intake requirements differ in various seasons of the year		
Yes		59(34.9%)	0.019*
No		46(27.2%)	
Don't know		64(37.9%)	
10.	Both men and women are at risk of vitamin D deficiency		
Yes		121(71.6%)	0.02*
No		32(18.9%)	
Don't know		16(9.5%)	

a Compares Medical and dental students.

b Categorical variables expressed as n (%).

* Denotes statistical significance $p < 0.05$.

Majority of the students reported that sun exposure is prevented by urbanization (77.4%). Vitamin D mainly is produced by sunlight falling on the skin. Skin has cholesterol that is converted to 7-dehydrocholesterol a precursor of vitamin D. A shortage in public places and full-time indoor occupation prevents the optimal exposure to the sun, making it difficult for the body to make vitamin D. This fact was realized by a bulk of the students participating in the study. 86.4% reported that shortage of public places prevents the sun exposure required for the production of vitamin D. Similarly 91.2% acknowledged the fact that full-time indoor occupation is harmful as well. The recommendation for supplements from these students wasn't strong.

Table .3 attitude analysis of students towards vitamin D

	Strongly agree	Agree	I don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Urbanization prevents sun exposure and the production of required vitamin D.	41(24.3%)	91(53.1%)	19(11.2%)	16(9.5%)	2(1.2%)
2. A shortage of public places for outdoor activities prevents the sun exposure required for production of vitamin D	45(26.6%)	101(59.8%)	15(8.9%)	6(3.6%)	2(1.2%)
3. Full-time indoor occupation prevents the sun exposure required for the production of vitamin D.	75(44.5%)	79(46.7%)	12(7.1%)	3(1.8%)	0
4. Inefficient education regarding the benefits of sun exposure prevents production of required vitamin D through sun exposure.	42(24.9%)	82(48.5%)	32(18.9%)	10(5.9%)	3(1.8%)
5. In vitamin D deficiency, supplement intake is more effective compared to dietary intake and sun exposure	15(8.9%)	31(18.3%)	60(35.5%)	54(35%)	9(5.3%)
6. Taking vitamin D supplement, unless recommended by physicians is wrong	28(16.6%)	75(45.5%)	44(26%)	20(11.8%)	2(1.2%)
7. The unwillingness of individuals to take vitamin D supplements is one of the barriers to providing this nutrient.	24(14.2%)	85(50.3%)	50(29.6%)	9(5.3%)	1(0.6%)
8. Taking supplements is necessary for the treatment of vitamin D deficiency but not for its prevention	24(14.2%)	76(44%)	51(30.2%)	17(10.1%)	1(0.6%)

The attitude of medical and dental students towards vitamin D was not to the point as only 10(5.8%) were taking vitamin D supplements and 14(8.3%) were consuming milk and foods rich in vitamin D. 26(15.5%) use sunscreens on their face 17(10%) on their hands regularly. Similarly their exposure to the sun and their outdoor activities are very limited.

Table.4 Showing a record of past 3 month's practices towards Vitamin D

	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1. For sufficient exposure to sunlight, I regularly engage in outdoor physical activities	17(10.1%)	41(24.3%)	56(31.3%)	43(25.4%)	12(7.1%)
2. To be vitamin D sufficient, I consume fortified milk	14(8.3%)	37(21.9%)	46(27.2%)	38(22.5%)	34(20.1%)
3. In order to be vitamin D sufficient, I consume fish at least twice a week	10(5.9%)	0	90(53.3%)	0	69(40.8%)
4. For sufficient exposure to sunlight, I walk outdoors daily	16(9.5%)	42(24.9%)	49(29%)	45(26.6%)	17(10.1%)
5. To be vitamin D sufficient, I take vitamin D supplements.					

	10(5.8%)	26(15.4%)	41(24.3%)	25(14.8%)	67(39.6%)
6.	I use sunscreen on my hands				
	17(10.1%)	19(11.2%)	24(14.2%)	36(21.3%)	73(43.2%)
7.	During the day I am directly exposed to sunlight (outdoors).				
	30(17.8%)	58(34.3%)	50(29.6%)	29(17.2%)	2(1.2%)
8.	During the day I am indirectly exposed to sunlight (through glass)				
	19(11.4%)	46(27.2%)	48(28.4%)	30(17.8%)	26(15.4%)
9.	I use sunscreen on my face				
	26(15.5%)	33(19.5%)	36(21.3%)	21(12.4%)	53(31.4%)

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge this is the only study till date in Pakistan, to evaluate the level of knowledge, attitude and practices. Our study is one among the only few which aim at understanding at knowledge, attitude and practices towards vitamin D among healthy university students in Pakistan, a country marked with high deficiency of vitamin D(1). Plus this study showed a clear picture that the knowledge, attitude and practices for supplementation is real poor though it helps. It is an important area of ongoing clinical concern.

University students are at a vital juncture in their formation of lifestyles that will have a significant impact on their future health(20,21). They are more likely to participate in harmful eating habits, such as fad diets, a high intake of fast meals, a low intake of fruits and vegetables, and a low intake of dairy products(21). Students of health sciences must develop healthy eating habits since they will become health-care professionals, and students who do not follow a healthy lifestyle are more likely to fail to persuade or promote health to their patients(17,21,22).

This study showed that the consumption of supplements of vitamin D is really low as only 5.9% were taking it. Though the level of knowledge about vitamin D among these dental and medical students was good enough despite the literature available(17,21,23). The study supporting our results is the demonstration of good level of knowledge about vitamin D in the UK(24). As recent studies showed that the level of knowledge was quite low across Canada, Japan, Sharjah, Saudi Arabia and Turkey (19,25–28). Another similar study in Rawalpindi reported, only half of the students (53.8%) had adequate general knowledge, which is unsatisfactory given that the participants are medical students, who will be the future forerunners of community health. Almost half of the participants (47%) had a strong understanding of nutrition. Furthermore, second-year students had greater nutritional awareness (64.7%), which is likely due to the fact that they are now studying biochemistry(29).

Despite having good knowledge about the importance of vitamin D and how it is produced, the attitude and practices was not sufficient. According to our research only 56 (31.1%) of the participants engage in outdoor activities making themselves exposed to the Sun. Less consumption of fish, fortified milk, supplements and other good sources of vitamin D was also reported. Only 17(10.1%) participants used sunscreen on their hands and 26(15.5%) on their faces. The relationship of attitude and practice towards vitamin D was consistent with the study done in Rawalpindi. Despite having good general and nutritional knowledge; only 32.9 percent of individuals had a positive attitude, which has a strong link to female gender. This is most likely due to the fact that girls are more concerned about their health than boys(29). 42% of individuals in a study did not take any supplements, but of those who did, females were the most probable supplement users(1). This discovery could be related to recent talks in the mainstream media that advise young women in their early twenties to get enough vitamin D and to take supplements(30).

To evaluate, multi-pronged tactics are required. Vitamin D is well-known and well-understood by the general public(15,23,26,28). People should be given information in their own tongues that reflects the current state of vitamin knowledge D and its link to health, as well as a firm understanding of it's importance and value(19). Our findings suggest that medical students are sufficiently knowledgeable about the benefits of vitamin D, but still health education is needed to improve their knowledge and behavior. Fortunately, the majority of students are curious about vitamin D. This is likely to be beneficial to health education. Our findings further support the necessity to spend more time outdoors. Furthermore, media campaigns and health professional counselling could be used to increase the use of vitamin D-rich foods.

Limitations

This survey had its limitation. This study was done on dental and medical students of Peshawar only, adding to that it was a cross sectional study, given only a snapshot picture of the real situation. Hence, it cannot be applicable on the general population. In addition, various innovative methods must be discovered to spread the knowledge on mass media to improve public awareness(1).

Conclusion

The medical and dental students of Peshawar were generally having good knowledge about vitamin D and the implications of vitamin D deficiency on our daily life. However, there attitudes and practices regarding vitamin D could be considered moderate. Despite the fact that they were medical and dental students, these statistics were not up to the mark. Such outcomes pose two dangers, both of which must be addressed at all costs. Firstly,

it would almost certainly cause vitamin D deficiency in those students, particularly ladies. Second, medical students are the guardians of their country's health; therefore their indifference to such a vital vitamin is inexcusable. Future studies should focus on strategies to make the knowledge about vitamin D more applicable in day to day life. Awareness of dietary supplement use and information should be integrated in to everyday practice with help of media coverage on the topic. Further studies are needed on vast scale to determine the knowledge, attitude and practices of people about vitamin D.

Reference

- Tariq A, Khan SR, Basharat A. Assessment of knowledge , attitudes and practice towards Vitamin D among university students in Pakistan. 2020;1–10.
- Jamil NA, Shahudin NN, Aziz NSA, Qi CJ, Aminuddin WAAW, Ludin AFM, et al. Knowledge, attitude and practice related to vitamin D and its relationship with vitamin d status among malay female office workers. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019;16(23):1–11.
- Section N, Rights A, Studios HD. No Title.
- Riaz H, Finlayson AE, Bashir S, Hussain S, Mahmood S, Malik F, et al. Prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency in Pakistan and implications for the future. *Expert Rev Clin Pharmacol [Internet]*. 2016 Feb 1;9(2):329–38. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1586/17512433.2016.1122519>
- Nadeem S, Munim TF, Hussain HF, Hussain DF. Determinants of Vitamin D deficiency in asymptomatic healthy young medical students. *Pakistan J Med Sci*. 2018;34(5):1248–52.
- Sharma S, Kumar A, Choudhary A, Sharma S, Khurana L, Sharma N, et al. Neuroprotective Role of Oral Vitamin D Supplementation on Consciousness and Inflammatory Biomarkers in Determining Severity Outcome in Acute Traumatic Brain Injury Patients: A Double-Blind Randomized Clinical Trial. *Clin Drug Investig [Internet]*. 2020;40(4):327–34. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40261-020-00896-5>
- Trial RC, Lerchbaum E, Trummer C, Theiler-schwetz V, Kollmann M, Wölfler M, et al. Effects of Vitamin D Supplementation on Body Composition and Metabolic Risk Factors in Men : A. 2019;
- Murtuza Rampurwala, MD, MPH [clinical instructor], Kari B. Wisinski, MD [associate professor], and Ruth O'Regan M [professor. 乳鼠心肌提取 HHS Public Access. *Physiol Behav*. 2017;176(12):139–48.
- Innocenti F, Owzar K, Jiang C, Etheridge AS, Gordân R, Sibley AB, et al. The Vitamin D receptor gene as a determinant of survival in pancreatic cancer patients: Genomic analysis and experimental validation. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(8):1–14.
- Mansouri L, Lundwall K, Moshfegh A, Jacobson SH, Lundahl J, Spaak J. Vitamin D receptor activation reduces inflammatory cytokines and plasma MicroRNAs in moderate chronic kidney disease - A randomized trial. *BMC Nephrol*. 2017;18(1):1–7.
- Holland A, Moffat T. Comparing measured calcium and vitamin D intakes with perceptions of intake in Canadian young adults: insights for designing osteoporosis prevention education. *Public Health Nutr*. 2017 Jul;20(10):1760–7.
- Amiri P, Asghari G, Sadrosadat H, Karimi M, Amouzegar A, Mirmiran P, et al. Psychometric properties of a developed questionnaire to assess knowledge, attitude and practice regarding vitamin D (D-KAP-38). *Nutrients*. 2017;9(5):1–13.
- Moorani KN, Mustufa MA, Hasan SF, Kubar N. Vitamin D status in under five children diverse communities of Karachi. *Pakistan J Med Sci*. 2019;35(2):414–9.
- Ansari SF, Memon M, Brohi N, Kumar B. Vitamin D and Serum Immunoglobulin E Levels in Allergic Rhinitis: A Case-control Study from Pakistan. *Cureus*. 2019;11(12).
- Alshamsan FM, Bin-Abbas BS. Knowledge, awareness, attitudes and sources of vitamin D deficiency and sufficiency in Saudi children. *Saudi Med J*. 2016;37(5):579–83.
- El Amrousy D, Hassan S, El Ashry H, Yousef M, Hodeib H. Vitamin D supplementation in adolescents with irritable bowel syndrome: Is it useful? A randomized controlled trial. *Saudi J Gastroenterol [Internet]*. 2018;24(2):109–14. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29637918>
- Algaheed HA, AlJaber MI, Alwehaibi AI, AlJaber LI, Arafah AM, Aloyayri MA, et al. General public knowledge and use of dietary supplements in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *J Fam Med Prim care [Internet]*. 2019 Oct 31;8(10):3147–54. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31742134>
- Bener A, Al-Ali M, Hoffmann GF. Vitamin D deficiency in healthy children in a sunny country: associated factors. *Int J Food Sci Nutr [Internet]*. 2009;60(sup5):60–70. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09637480802400487>
- Goodman S, Morrongiello B, Meckling K. A randomized, controlled trial evaluating the efficacy of an online intervention targeting vitamin D intake, knowledge and status among young adults. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act [Internet]*. 2016;13(1):1–13. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12966-016-0443-1>
- Geng C, Shaikh AS, Han W, Chen D, Guo Y, Jiang P. Vitamin D and depression: mechanisms, determination and application. *Asia Pac J Clin Nutr*. 2019;28(4):689–94.

- Zhou M, Zhuang W, Yuan Y, Li Z, Cai Y. Investigation on Vitamin D knowledge, attitude and practice of university students in Nanjing, China. *Public Health Nutr.* 2016;19(1):78–82.
- Alhomoud FK, Basil M, Bondarev A. Knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) relating to dietary supplements among health sciences and non-health sciences students in one of the universities of United Arab Emirates (UAE). *J Clin Diagnostic Res.* 2016;10(9).
- KNOWLEDGE , ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE STUDY ON THE POPULATION OF NAHAKI REGARDING CONSANGUINITY AND ITS ASSOCIATED REPRODUCTIVE RISKS. :1–5.
- O'Connor C, Glatt D, White L, Revuelta Iniesta R. Knowledge, Attitudes and Perceptions towards Vitamin D in a UK Adult Population: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2018 Oct;15(11).
- Salmanpour VA, Ibrahim HS, Salameh AG, Yahya AM, Debal BK. Vitamin D deficiency: knowledge and practices among the adult population in Sharjah, United Arab Emirates. *Arch Osteoporos [Internet].* 2016;11(1):1–7. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11657-016-0269-0>
- Al-rasheedi M, Alrajhi M, Alqahtani SS, Alsuhaibani S, Kardam A, Alhazmi Y. Knowledge of Dietary Supplements among Women in the Aseer Region of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. 2020;32(November 2019):71–86.
- Matsunaga T, Nishikawa K, Adachi T, Yasuda K. Associations between dietary consumption and sleep quality in young Japanese males. *Sleep Breath.* 2020;
- Kafadar D, Sayin E. Knowledge and attitudes towards vitamin / mineral supplements in patients admitted to the family medicine outpatient clinics. *J Turkish Fam Physician.* 2020;11(2):56–67.
- Shalaby SF, Soliman MA. Knowledge, attitude, and practice of medical students regarding smoking and substance abuse, cairo university, egypt. *J Egypt Public Health Assoc.* 2019;94(1):1–9.
- Bokharee N, Khan YH, Wasim T, Mallhi TH, Alotaibi NH, Iqbal MS, et al. Daily versus stat Vitamin D supplementation during pregnancy; A prospective cohort study. *PLoS One [Internet].* 2020;15(4):1–17. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231590>

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